

The biogeographical distribution of species of the superfamily Coreoidea: Hemiptera in India

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ABSTRACT

The present paper deals with 151 species belonging to 59 genera distributed over 14 tribes, 16 divisions, 7 subfamilies and 4 families under the Superfamily Coreoidea.

INTRODUCTION

Coreoidea is a large Superfamily of predominantly herbivorous insects that belong in the Hemipteran Suborder Heteroptera. The Superfamily Coreoidea is divided into 4 families namely Coreidae, Stenocephalidae, Alydidae, Rhopalidae but the Coreoidea as a whole are part of a close-knit group with the Lygaeoidea and Pyrrhocoroidea and it is likely that these three super families are paraphyletic to a significant extent. They are therefore in need of revision and red limitation. There are more than 3400 species recorded in the world.

The insects of the family Coreidae vary from 7 to 45 mm, making the larger species some of the big heteropterans (Sehuh and Slater, 1950). The body shape of these insects is quite variable, with some species broadly oval while others are slender. Coreids are found throughout the world but most species are found in the tropics and subtropics. They are also called “leaf-footed bugs and squash bugs” due to the leaf like expansions some species have on their hind leg. These bugs feed on the shoots, buds, fruits and unripe seeds of many plants throughout the world. Thoracic scent glands produce strong

smelling, defensive chemicals. Some species are considered serious pests. The general morphological features of Coreidae are oval shaped body, antennae composed of 4 segments, numerous veined forewing membrane, a metathoracic stink gland and enlarged hind tibia. Many species are covered with spines and tubercles. Antennae 4 segmented ; ocelli 2 ; beak 4 segmented ; front wing with many veins ; tarsi 3 segmented ; scent glands present on the thorax ; head narrower than and often shorter than the pronotum ; hind tibia of some species expanded and resembling leaves. The species in the family Coreidae are separated from those in Alydidae by differences in width and length of their heads relative to the pronotum. There are more than 1800 species have been recorded under this family in the world.

The family Stenocephalidae is represented by only one (*Dicranocephalus*) genera. They are commonly called as spurge bugs. These are phytophagous insects. They feed on *Euphorbia* species. They are small to large in size. Length of the body ranges from 8-14 mm long; fliers; relatively stout bodied; not stilt-legged; with conspicuous dark and pale banding on the antennae and legs. Head non-linear. Rostrum clearly separated ventrally from the prosternum

by a sclerotized gula; 4 segmented. Antennae longer than the head, readily visible from above; 4 segmented; non-striae. Ocelli present. Scutellum relatively small. Forewings well developed; differentiated into a basally thickened and distally membranous region with a clavus. Membrane of the hemelytron with numerous veins reaching or almost reaching the margin. Tarsi 3 segmented. The abdomen without ventral silvery pubescence. The second dorsal abdominal scent gland aperture not displaced into the fifth tergite and distant from the first gland. They are dark-brown bugs with black and yellow banded antennae, front of the head bilobed.

Alydidae commonly called broad headed bugs, have a head that is nearly as wide as and as long as the pronotum. It is similar to Coreidae, but buccula not extending past base of antennae; these are common and notable because of their noxious smell and the nymphs that resemble ants. They feed on plants.

The body length of the members of the family Rhopalidae the Scentless plant bugs range from 4 to 15 mm. They vary greatly in shape and colour. The majority are dull brownish and resemble species of Orsillinae (Lygaeidae), with which one often finds them confused in collections. The remainder is much larger and similar in shape, body form and bright colouration to species of Lygaeinae and many species of Pyrrhocoreidae and Largidae. The clypeus surpassing mandibular plates ; ocelli situated on low tubercles ; antennae never dilated, first segment constricted basally ; metathoracic scent gland openings usually obsolete or obsolescent ; corium frequently with large hyaline areas ; membrane of forewing always with numerous veins ; tricothira on abdominal sterna 3 and 4 mediolateral, those of 5, 6 and 7 lateral ; abdominal spiracles ventral ; inner laterotergites present ; nymphs with dorsal abdominal scent gland openings between terga 4/5 and 5/6 the later displaced forward, a unique and universally occurring character in the family ; pygophore with lateral, median and paralaral lobes ; ovipositor plate-like ; abdominal sternum 7 of females entire ; spermatheca consisting of a

round bulb, small pump and long, generally coiled duct. They feed on the seeds of box elder and aggregate on the sunny, south facing sides of the houses in the fall, looking for sites to overwinter.

Some important workers on the taxonomy and distribution of Coreoidea are : Agassiz (1843), Basu & Mitra (1977, 1978, 1996, 2003, 2004), Dallas (1852), Distant (1902, 1904, 1908, 1918), Dohrn (1859), Dolling (2006), Fallen (1814), Gollner-Scheiding (1980), Hahn (1826), Herrich-Schaffer (1853), Horvath (1917), Kerzhner (1962), Kirklydy (1903), Latreille (1829), Lethirey & Severin (1894), O'Shea & C. W. Schaefer (1980), Putshkov, V. G. & Kerzhner (1983), Schmidt (1911), Stål (1866, 1871, 1873), Van Duzee (1914), Walker (1871, 1873), White (1839) etc.

Figure-1 Biogeographic Regions of India

The insects are known to be most successful and diverse animals on earth. They have adapted for almost every conceivable type of environment from the equator to the arctic and from sea level to the snowfield of highest mountain, on land, in air and water and almost everywhere. Coreoids are found throughout the world but most species are found in the tropics and subtropics. The

Coreoidea fauna on the oriental region comprises of 212 species and the Indian fauna pertains to 160 species belonging to 59 genera which are about 5% of the world fauna.

Biogeography is the study of the distribution of species, organisms and ecosystems in space and through geological time. Organisms and biological communities vary in a highly regular fashion along geographic gradients of latitude, elevation, isolation and habitat area. Knowledge of spatial variation in the numbers and types of organisms is as vital to us today as it was to our early human ancestors, as we adapt to heterogeneous but geographically predictable environments. Biogeography is an interactive field of inquiry that unites concepts and information from ecology, evolutionary biology, geology and physical geography. Modern biogeographic research combines information and ideas from many fields, from the physiological and ecological constraints on organismal dispersal to geological and climatological phenomena operating at global spatial scales and evolutionary time frames.

An ecoregion (Biogeographic region) sometimes called a bioregion, is an ecologically and geographically defined area that is smaller than an ecozone and larger than an ecosystem. Ecoregions cover relatively large areas of land or water and contain characteristic geographically distinct assemblages of natural communities and species. The biodiversity of flora, fauna and ecosystems that characterizes an ecoregion tends to be distinct from that of other ecoregions. India has a highly variable natural continuum divided into 8 major separate biogeographic regions (Ecoregions). They are the Himalayan, the Desert, the Arid and Semiarid, the Western Ghats, the Deccan Plateau, the Gangetic plain, the Northeast India and the Islands. The regions discerned primarily according to Rodgers, Panwar and Mathur, 2002. Since, only one hemipteran family is dealt with, further divisions of these regions into sub regions has been avoided so as to yield numerically significant data.

The Trans-Himalayan region

The Trans-Himalayan region of India consists of the cold deserts of Ladakh and Kargil in Jammu and Kashmir, and the Lahaul and Spiti valleys of Himachal Pradesh. Ladakh, located at the edge of the Tibetan plateau, gets an annual rainfall of only 140 mm. The major portion of the precipitation occurs in the form of snow in the winter months and, hence, cannot be used for agriculture. Kargil district is nestled in the Himalayas, giving it a cool, temperate climate. Summers are warm with cool nights, while winters are long and cold with temperatures often dropping to -40°C (-40°F) with recorded temperatures of -60°C (-76°F) in the tiny town of Dras, situated some 56 km (35 mi) from the Kargil town. The Zaskar plateau is even colder, making it thus a near-uninhabitable place for humans, except for the hardy Khampas. The entire Kargil district is spread over 14,086 km² (5,439 sq mi). The Suru River flows through the district. The Lahaul-Spiti bounded by Tibet in the east and Ladakh in the north, the Lahaul-Spiti district of Himachal Pradesh is located at a mean elevation of 3,048-4,572 m. The low monsoon clouds get blocked by the high mountains and leave the area dry and devoid of vegetation.

The Himalayan region

The Himalayan region consists of Jammu & Kashmir, parts of Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Sikkim, Darjeeling district of West Bengal and some parts of Arunachal Pradesh. It has a forest cover of almost all types like the tropical wet evergreen, subtropical pine, montane wet temperate, Himalayan moist and dry temperate, as well as sub alpine and alpine forests. Temperature fluctuations in this region are also high, from below 0°C in winter on the snow-clad peaks to around 30°C in the foothills in summer.

The Northeast Indian region

This region is primarily a hilly region covering the “seven sisters” or the states of Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram,

Nagaland and Tripura and physiographically spreads over Naga, Patkai, Khasi, Jaintia, Garo, Lusai, Mikir hills and a part of eastern Himalayas. Vegetation in this area is mainly tropical wet evergreen, semi-evergreen and moist deciduous forests, subtropical broad leaved hill and pine forests, and montane wet temperate forests. Average rainfall is around 250 to 300 cm with some regions of Assam and Meghalaya receiving over 500 cm of rainfall. Summer temperature is around 7°C to 20°C and winter temperature is around 2°C to 18°C.

The Gangetic Plains

The gangetic plains is the entire fertile stretch of low lying plains on either side of the river Ganges covering the states of Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, parts of West Bengal. Vegetation in this region is mainly tropical, semi-evergreen, moist deciduous, swampy and dry deciduous forest. Mean annual temperature in summer is over 24°C and 18°C in winter with an annual rainfall of 100-200 cm.

The semi-arid region

The region is typified by low rainfall and sparse vegetation spreading over the majority areas of Gujarat, parts of Rajasthan, Haryana and Punjab. This area experiences extremes of weather conditions. Winter is cold; with temperatures as low as 4°C and summer is extremely hot around 45°C. The area receives an annual rainfall of 300-500 mm. Vegetation is usually dry deciduous tropical forests and dry grasslands.

The Desert region

The Thar desert also known as the Great Indian Desert is a large, arid region in the northwestern part of the Indian subcontinent with an area of more than 2, 00,000 sq. km. It is the 9th largest subtropical desert in the world. It lies mostly in the Indian states of Rajasthan, and extends into the southern portion of Haryana and Punjab states and into northern Gujarat state. There are three principal landforms in the desert region. The predominantly sand covered Thar, the plains with hills including the central dune free country

and the semiarid areas surrounding the Aravalli range. The natural vegetation is classed as northern desert thorn forest (Champion, 1936). These occur in small clumps scattered in a more or less open forms.

The Deccan plateau region

The Deccan plateau spreading over the states of Maharashtra, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, parts of Odisha, Pudhucherry and Tamil Nadu. The plateau part of the Deccan peninsula covers an area of 7, 00,000 sq. km. with an average altitude of 600 m (Alfred *et al.*, 2000). A major part of the Deccan plateau is covered by dry deciduous forests and degraded scrubland. The Eastern Ghats is an assemblage of discontinuous ranges of hills, plateaus and escarpments with an elevation around 1750 m. The Eastern Ghats receives an average rainfall of 120-160 cm. In the summer the maximum temperature is 41°C while winter is as low as 2°C. Forest cover in the Eastern Ghats is broadly evergreen, semi-evergreen, tropical, moist deciduous, southern tropical dry deciduous, northern mixed dry deciduous, dry savannah and dry evergreen scrub.

The Western Ghats

The Western Ghats also known as Shyadri Mountains is mountain range along the western side of India. It runs north to south along the western edge of the Deccan plateau and separates the plateau from a narrow coastal plain along the Arabian Sea. The range starts near the border of Gujarat and Maharashtra, south of the river Tapti and runs approximately 1600 kms through the states of Maharashtra, Goa, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Kerala ending at Kanyakumari at the southern tip of India. About 60% of the Western Ghats are located in the state of Karnataka. These hills cover 60,000 sq. km and form the catchment area for a complex of river systems that drain almost 40% of India. The average elevation is around 1200 meters. The area is one of the world's ten hottest biodiversity hotspots.

The climate is humid and tropical in the lower reaches tempered by the proximity to the sea. Average annual temperature here is around 15°C. In some parts frost is common and temperatures touch the freezing point during the winter months. Mean temperature range from 20°C in the south to 24°C in the north. The Western Ghats are home to four tropical and subtropical moist broadleaf forest ecoregions. They are the northwestern Ghats moist deciduous forests, north Western Ghats montane rain forests, south Western Ghats moist deciduous forests and south Western Ghats montane rain forests. The evergreen Wayanad forests of Kerala mark the transition zone between the northern and southern ecoregions of Western Ghats. The southern ecoregions are generally wetter and more species rich.

The Islands

Indian limits include two different island groups viz, the Andaman and Nicobar Islands lying in the Bay of Bengal and the Lakshadweep islands in the Arabian Sea. The Andaman Islands are an arcuate chain of more than 500 islands, islets and rocky outcrops running north to south in the Bay of Bengal extending over 800 kms. (Alfred *et al.*, 2001). Lakshadweep archipelago is irregularly scattered in the south Arabian Sea and stretches about 2500 km in the ocean along north south direction (Alfred *et al.*, 2001). The archipelago comprises of 36 islands including 12 atolls, 3 reefs and 5 submerged banks with a total land area of 32 sq. km. vegetation in the Andaman is a varied mosaic of tropical evergreen, semi-evergreen, moist deciduous, littoral forests and mangroves. Climate in this region is tropical with temperature around 23° to 30°C and 300 cm of rainfall.

The Coasts

The Eastern Coastal Plain is a wide stretch of land lying between the Eastern Ghats and the Bay of Bengal. It stretches from Tamil Nadu in the south to West Bengal in the east. The Mahanadi, Godavari, Kaveri, and Krishna rivers drain these plains. The temperature in the coastal regions often exceeds 30 °C (86 °F), and is

coupled with high levels of humidity. The region receives both the northeast monsoon and southwest monsoon rains. The southwest monsoon splits into two branches, the Bay of Bengal branch and the Arabian Sea branch. The Bay of Bengal branch moves northwards crossing northeast India in early June. The Arabian Sea branch moves northwards and discharges much of its rain on the windward side of Western Ghats. Annual rainfall in this region averages between 1,000 and 3,000 mm (39 and 120 in). The width of the plains varies between 100 and 130 km (62 and 81 mi). The plains are divided into six regions- the Mahanadi delta, the southern Andhra Pradesh plain, the Krishna-Godavari deltas, the Kanyakumari coast, the Coromandel Coast, and sandy coastal.

The Western Coastal Plain is a narrow strip of land sandwiched between the Western Ghats and the Arabian Sea, ranging from 50 to 100 km (31 to 62 mi) in width. It extends from Gujarat in the north and extends through Maharashtra, Goa, Karnataka, and Kerala. Numerous rivers and backwaters inundate the region. Mostly originating in the Western Ghats, the rivers are fast-flowing, usually perennial, and empty into estuaries. Major rivers flowing into the sea are the Tapi, Narmada, Mandovi and Zuari. Vegetation is mostly deciduous, but the Malabar Coast moist forests constitute a unique ecoregion. The Western Coastal Plain can be divided into two parts, the Konkan and the Malabar Coast.

SYSTEMATIC LIST

Order **HEMIPTERA**
 Suborder **HETEROPTERA**
 Infraorder **PENTATOMOMORPHA**
 Superfamily **COREOIDEA**
 Family **COREIDAE**
 Subfamily **COREINAE**
 Division **Mictaria**
 Tribe **Mictini** Amyot & Serville, 1843
 Genus ***Molipteryx*** Kiritshenko, 1916
 1916. *Molipteryx* Kiritshenko, *Fauna Rossii*.
Nasekomye poluzhestkokrylye (Insecta
 Hemiptera) **6(2):27, 32-42.**

1. *Molipteryx hardwickii hardwickii* (White, 1839)
1839. *Derepteryx hardwickii* White, *Mag. Nat. Hist.* (n.s.) **3**: 542: Nepal.
Distribution: Assam and Sikkim.
Genus *Derepteryx* White, 1839
1839. *Derepteryx* White, *Mag. Nat. Hist.* (n.s.) **3**:542.
2. *Derepteryx grayii* White, 1839
1839. *Derepteryx grayii* White, *Mag. Nat. Hist.* (n.s.) **3**:542: Nepal.
Distribution: Sikkim and West Bengal.
Genus *Helcomeria* Stål, 1873
1873. *Helcomeria* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2):37, 40.
3. *Helcomeria spinosa* (Signoret, 1851)
1851. *Petascelis spinosus* Signoret, *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* **29**: 123-124.
Distribution: Assam, Nagaland, Sikkim and West Bengal (Singla and Darjeeling district).
Genus *Prionolomia* Stål, 1873
1873. Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2):37, 40.
4. *Prionolomia cardoni* Lethierry, 1891
1891. *Prionolomia cardoni* Lethierry, *Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg.* **35**: cxliii – cxliv. Bengal, Kunbir.
Distribution: West Bengal.
5. *Prionolomia fulvicornis* (Fabricius, 1787)
1787. *Cimex fulvicornis* Fabricius, *Mantissa insectorum sistens species nuper detectas adjectis synonymis, observationibus, descriptionibus, emendationibus* **2**: 288.
Distribution: Assam and Sikkim.
6. *Prionolomia gigas* Distant, 1879
1879. *Prionolomia gigas* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **53**: 127-129: India.
Distribution: Assam and Sikkim.
Genus *Prionolomiopsis* O'Shea, 1980
1980. O'Shea, In O'Shea & C. W. Schaefer, A generic revision of the Asian and Australian Mictini (Heteroptera: Coreidae). *Oriental Insects* **14**(2):222, 246-247.
7. *Prionolomiopsis amplicolis* (Stål, 1873)
1873. *Mygdonia amplicolis* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 43 – 44: Bangladesh.
Distribution: Nagaland.
Genus *Ochrochira* Stål, 1873
1873. Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 39, 44.
8. *Ochrochira aberrans* (Distant, 1889)
1889. *Prionolomia aberrans* Distant, *Ent. Mon. Mag.* **25**: 230. NZSI, Kolkata.
Distribution: Assam and Sikkim.
9. *Ochrochira albiditarsis* (Westwood, 1842)
1842. *Myctis albiditarsis* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 4, 11: Nepal.
Distribution: Himachal Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh.
10. *Ochrochira biplagiata* (Walker, 1871)
1871. *Mictis biplagiata* Walker, Catalogue of the Specimens of Hemiptera Heteroptera in the Collection of the British Museum **IV**: 21-23: Northern India.
Distribution: Assam, Sikkim and West Bengal (Rongirum, Peshok, Siliguri of Darjeeling district).
11. *Ochrochira pallescens* Distant, 1889
1889. *Ochrochira pallescens* Distant, *Ent. Mon. Mag.* **25**: 230.
Distribution: Assam and Sikkim.
12. *Ochrochira palliditarsis* Stål, 1873
1873. *Ochrochira palliditarsis* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 44: India.
Distribution: Northeast India.
Genus *Mictis* Leach, 1814
1814. Leach, the Zoological Miscellany, being descriptions of new, or interesting Animals **1**: 91.
13. *Mictis gallina* Dallas, 1852
1852. *Mictis gallina* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 403 – 404: India.
Distribution: Assam.
14. *Mictis macra* Stål, 1865
1865. *Mictis macra* Stål, *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* **45**:173 – 174: Malaya, Malacca and Thailand, Ligor; NHRS Stockholm.
Distribution: Kerala.
15. *Mictis tenebrosa* Fabricius, 1787)
1787. *Cimex tenebrosus* Fabricius, *Mantissa insectorum sistens species nuper detectas adjectis synonymis, observationibus, descriptionibus, emendationibus* **2**: 288. rec. East India.
Distribution: Assam, Nagaland, Sikkim and West Bengal.

Genus *Aspilosterna* Stål, 1873

1873. *Mictis* (*Aspilosterna*) Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 46-47.

16. *Aspilosterna pictor* (Fabricius, 1794)

1794. *Lygaeus Pictor* Fabricius, *Entomologia systematica emendata et aucta secundum classes, ordines, genera, species adjectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus* 4: 138.

Distribution: Assam.

Genus *Neomictis* O'Shea & Schaefer, 1980

1980. O'Shea & C. W. Schaefer, *Oriental Insects* **14**(2): 224, 231.

17. *Neomictis filicornis* (Walker, 1871)

1871. *Mictis filicornis* Walker, *Catalogue of the Specimens of Hemiptera Heteroptera in the Collection of the British Museum* **IV**: 25, 27.

Distribution: Sikkim. **Elsewhere:** Borneo.

Genus *Anoplocnemis* Stål, 1873

1873. Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 39, 47-50.

18. *Anoplocnemis binotata* Distant, 1918

1918. *Anoplocnemis binotata* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota. Vol. 7*: 153.

Distribution: Assam.

19. *Anoplocnemis phasianus* (Fabricius, 1781)

1781. *Cimex phasianus* Fabricius, *Species Insectorum exhibentes eorum differentias specificas, synonyma auctorum, loca natalia, metamorphosin adiectis observationibus, descriptionibus.* **2**:89.

Distribution: Assam, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Nagaland, Sikkim and West Bengal (Darjeeling and Buxaduar, Jalpaiguri district).

20. *Anoplocnemis protracta* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850)

1850. *Mictis protractus* Herrich-Schäffer, *Die wanzenartigen Insecten* **9**: 247.

Distribution: Assam and Uttarakhand (Dehradun).

Genus *Xyrophoreus* Breddin, 1909

1909. Breddin, *Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg.* **53**: 283.

21. *Xyrophoreus cristatus* Brailovsky & Barrera, 2000

2000. *Xyrophoreus cristatus* Brailovsky & Barrera, *J. New York Entom. Soc.* **108**(1-2):146-150.

Distribution: Karnataka (Mysore).

Division **Petasclaria**

Tribe **Petascelini** Stål, 1873

Genus *Trematocoris* Mayr, 1865

1865. Mayr, *Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien* **15**:431

22. *Trematocoris lobipes* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Myctis lobipes* Westwood, *A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope.* **2**: 11.

Distribution: Karnataka (Belghaum), Maharashtra and West Bengal (Shibpur in Howrah district)

23. *Trematocoris notatipes* Walker, 1871

1871. *Trematocoris notatipes* Walker, *Catalogue of the Specimens of Hemiptera Heteroptera in the Collection of the British Museum* **IV**: 32, 34.

Distribution: Bihar and West Bengal.

Genus *Petillopsis* Hsiao, 1963

1963. Hsiao, *Acta Zoologica Sinica* **15**: 614-615, 622.

24. *Petillopsis calcar* (Dallas, 1852)

1852. *Mictis calcar* Dallas, *List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum* **II**: 397-398.

Distribution: Assam, Maharashtra, Manipur, Odisha, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Sukna and Peshok in Darjeeling district).

25. *Petillopsis patulicollis* (Walker, 1871)

1871. *Trematocoris patulicollis* Walker, *Catalogue of the Specimens of Hemiptera Heteroptera in the Collection of the British Museum* **IV**: 33, 37.

Distribution: Nagaland, Sikkim and West Bengal (Kurseong in Darjeeling district and buxa Tiger Reserve in Jalpaiguri district).

Division **Daladeria**

Tribe **Daladerini** Stål, 1873

Genus *Dalader* Amyot & Serville, 1843

1843. Amyot & Serville, *Histoire naturelle des insectes. Hémiptères* **xxxi**, 187-188.

26. *Dalader acuticosta* Amyot & Serville, 1843

1843. *Dalader acuticosta* Amyot & Serville, *Histoire naturelle des insectes. Hémiptères* **188**.

Distribution: Assam, Sikkim and West Bengal (Mirik, Darjeeling district and Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district).

Elsewhere: Borneo.

27. *Dalader planiventris* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Acanonicus planiventris* Westwood, *A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope.* **2**: 8.

Distribution: Assam, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Division **Brachytaria**

Genus **Brachytes** Westwood, 1842

1842. Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**:8.

28. *Brachytes bicolor* Westwood, 1842

1842. *Brachytes bicolor* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 8-9.

Distribution: Assam, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Odisha (Chilka Lake).

Division **Homoceraria**

Tribe **Homoeocerini** Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus **Aschistocoris** Bergroth, 1909

1909. Bergroth, *Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg.* **53**: 34, 57, 63.

29. *Aschistocoris brevicornis* (Dallas, 1852)

1852. *Ornytus brevicornis* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 448.

Distribution: Madhya Pradesh and Sikkim.

Genus **Homoeocerus** Burmeister, 1835

1835. Burmeister, *Handbuch der Entomologie* 300, 303, 316.

Subgenus **Anacanthocoris** Uhler, 1861

30. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris)*

albiguttulus Stål, 1873

1873. *Homoeocerus albiguttulus* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 61.

Distribution: Assam, Odisha, Sikkim and West Bengal (Kolkata and Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district).

31. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) albiventris* Dallas, 1852

1852. *Homoeocerus albiventris* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 444 – 445.

Distribution: Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

32. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) angulatus* Westwood, 1842

1842. *Homoeocerus angulatus* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 5, 22.

Distribution: Kerala, Sikkim and West Bengal (Singla, Darjeeling district).

33. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) biguttatus* Westwood, 1842

1842. *Homoeocerus biguttatus* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 5, 22.

Distribution: Sikkim.

34. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) concisus* Walker, 1871

1871. *Homoeocerus concisus* Walker, Catalogue of the Specimens of Hemiptera Heteroptera in the Collection of the British Museum **IV**: 92, 97.

Distribution: Assam and Sikkim.

35. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) fasciolatus* Stål, 1873

1873. *Homoeocerus fasciolatus* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 60 – 61.

Distribution: Sikkim.

36. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) graminis* (Fabricius, 1803)

1803. *Lygaeus graminis* Fabricius, *Systema Rhyngotorum secundum ordines, genera, speciesadjectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus.* 216.

Distribution: Assam.

37. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) javanicus* Dallas, 1852

1852. *Homoeocerus javanicus* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 369-592.

Distribution: Assam.

38. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) lacertosus* Distant, 1889

1889. *Homoeocerus lacertosus* Distant, *Ent. Mon. Mag.* **25**: 230-231.

Distribution: Punjab.

39. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) macula* Dallas, 1852

1852. *Homoeocerus macula* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 445.

Distribution: Tamil Nadu.

40. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) simiolus* Distant, 1902

1902. *Homoeocerus simiolus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma.* Rhynchota 1 (Heteroptera): 363.

Distribution: Assam, Meghalaya, Sikkim and West Bengal (Peshok in Darjeeling district).

- 41. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) striicornis*** Scott, 1874
1874. *Homoeocerus striicornis* Scott, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **414**: 362.
Distribution: Assam, Maharashtra, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Darjeeling and Jalpaiguri).
- 42. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) subjectus*** Walker, 1871
1871. *Homoeocerus subjectus* Walker, Catalogue of the Specimens of Hemiptera Heteroptera in the Collection of the British Museum **IV**: 92, 97.
Distribution: Assam.
- 43. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) tinctus*** Distant, 1883
1883. *Homoeocerus tinctus* Distant, *Trans. Ent. Soc. London* **1883**: 170.
Distribution: West Bengal (Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district).
- 44. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) walkeri*** Kirby, 1892
1892. *Homoeocerus walkeri* Kirby, *Journal of the Linnean Society of London* **24**: 91.
Distribution: Assam, Nagaland, Sikkim and West Bengal (Peshok in Darjeeling district and Jayanti Village in Buxa Tiger Reserve of Jalpaiguri district).
Subgenus *Tliponius* Stål, 1860
- 45. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) atkinsoni*** Distant, 1901
1901. *Homoeocerus atkinsoni* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77(37)**: 10, 11.
Distribution: Assam and Nagaland.
- 46. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) badgleyi*** Distant, 1908
1908. *Homoeocerus badgleyi* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota **4** (2): 468.
Distribution: Assam.
- 47. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) indus*** Distant, 1918
1918. *Homoeocerus indus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota. Vol. **7**: 156.
Distribution: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikkanal) and Uttarakhand (Kumaon Hills).
- 48. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) laevilineus*** Stål, 1873
1873. *Homoeocerus laevilineus* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11(2)**: 85.
Distribution: Assam and Maharashtra.
- 49. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) montanus*** Distant, 1901
1901. *Homoeocerus montanus* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77(37)**: 11.
Distribution: Tamil Nadu.
- 50. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) nigradorsum*** Horváth, 1889
1889. *Homoeocerus nigradorsum* Horváth, *Természetrázi Füzetek* **12**: 34-35.
Distribution: Himalaya and Tamil Nadu.
- 51. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) picturatus*** Distant, 1918
1918. *Homoeocerus picturatus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota. Vol. **7**: 155.
Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).
- 52. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) puncticornis*** (Burmeister, 1834)
1834. *Coreus puncticornis* Burmeister, Beiträge zur Zoologie, gesammelt auf einer Reise um die Erde, und W. Erichson's und H. Burmeister's Beschreibungen und Abbildungen der von Herrn Meyen auf dieser Reise gesammelten Insekten. Nova Acta Academiae Caesareae Leopoldino-Carolinae Naturae Curiosorum **16**: 295.
Distribution: India.
- 53. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) punctum*** Dallas, 1852
1852. *Homoeocerus punctum* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 446.
Distribution: Sikkim.
- 54. *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) serrifer*** (Westwood, 1842)
1842. *Coreus serrifer* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 6, 24.
Distribution: Assam, Sikkim and West Bengal (Peshok in Darjeeling district).
Genus *Prismatocerus* Amyot & Serville, 1843
1843. Amyot & Serville, *Histoire naturelle des insectes*. Hémiptères 184 – 185.
- 55. *Prismatocerus apicicornis*** (Distant, 1918)
1918. *Homoeocerus apicicornis* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota. Vol. **7**: 154-155.
Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).

56. *Prismatocerus borealis* (Distant, 1918)
1918. *Homoeocerus borealis* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota. Vol. 7: 155, 156.

Distribution: Uttarakhand (Dehradun).

57. *Prismatocerus cordiger* (Stål, 1860)
1860. *Tliponius cordiger* Stål, *Öfvers. K. VetenskAkad. Förh. Stockh* **16**: 465.

Distribution: Kerala.

58. *Prismatocerus inornatus* (Stål, 1873)
1873. *Homoeocerus inornatus* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 58-59.

Distribution: Goa, Odisha, Pudhucherry, Sikkim and West Bengal (Peshok in Darjeeling district).

59. *Prismatocerus prominulus* (Dallas, 1852)
1852. *Ceratopachys prominulus* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 501.

Distribution: Maharashtra.

60. *Prismatocerus sigillatus* (Stål, 1873)
1873. *Homoeocerus sigillatus* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2): 59.

Distribution: Sikkim and Uttarakhand.

61. *Prismatocerus signatus* (Walker, 1871)
1871. *Homoeocerus signatus* Walker, Catalogue of the Specimens of Hemiptera Heteroptera in the Collection of the British Museum **IV**: 92, 97.

Distribution: Kerala, Maharashtra, Sikkim and West Bengal (Peshok in Darjeeling and Buxa Tiger Reserve in Jalpaiguri district).

Tribe **Anhomoeini** Hsiao, 1964

Genus **Anhomoeus** Hsiao, 1963

1963. Hsiao, *Acta Entomologica Sinica* **12**: 312, 327, 341.

62. *Anhomoeus nepalensis* (Distant, 1908)
1908. *Aschistus nepalensis* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota **4** (2): 468.

Distribution: Uttarakhand and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Nepal.

63. *Anhomoeus sulcatus* (Distant, 1908)
1908. *Aschistus sulcatus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota **4** (2): 469-470.

Distribution: Uttarakhand (sabhawala, Dehradun). **Elsewhere:** Myanmar.

Genus *Omanocoris* Kiritshenko, 1916

1916. Kiritshenko, Fauna Rossii. Nasekomye poluzhestkokrylye (Insecta Hemiptera) **6**(2): 29, 68, 69, 83 -100.

64. *Omanocoris versicolor* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1841)

1841. *Gonocerus versicolor* Herrich-Schäffer, *Die wanzenartigen Insecten* **6**: 58 - 59, plate 199, fig. 619.

Distribution: Kerala, North India, Sikkim and Tamil Nadu.

Division **Cloresmaria**

Tribe **Cloresmini** Stål, 1873

Genus **Notobitus** Stål, 1860

1860. Stål, *Öfvers. K. Vetensk Akad. Förh. Stockh* **16**: 451.

65. *Notobitus abdominalis* Distant, 1901
1901. *Notobitus abdominalis* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77**(37): 13.

Distribution: Assam and Nagaland.

66. *Notobitus dorsalis* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Nematopus dorsalis* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 4, 13.

Distribution: Maharashtra and West Bengal.

67. *Notobitus excellens* Distant, 1879
1879. *Notobitus excellens* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **53**: 127.

Distribution: Assam, Meghalaya, Nagaland and Sikkim.

68. *Notobitus marginalis* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Nematopus marginalis* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 4, 14.

Distribution: Meghalaya, Nagaland and West Bengal.

69. *Notobitus meleagris* (Fabricius, 1787)
1787. *Cimex meleagris* Fabricius, Mantissa insectorum sistens species nuper detectas adjectis synonymis, observationibus, descriptionibus, emendationibus **2**: 297.

Distribution: Kerala, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal. **Elsewhere:** China.

Distribution: Meghalaya, Nagaland and West Bengal.

70. *Notobitus serripes* (Dallas, 1850)

1850. *Nematopus serripes* Dallas, *Trans. Ent. Soc. London New series* **1**: 4-5.

Distribution: Assam, Nagaland and Sikkim. **Elsewhere:** Bhutan.

Genus *Cloresmus* Stål, 1860

1860. *Öfvers. K. Vetensk Akad. Förh. Stockh* **16**: 451.

71. *Cloresmus antennatus* Distant, 1908

1908. *Cloresmus antennatus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma.*

Rhynchota **4** (2): 471-472.

Distribution: Assam, Sikkim and West Bengal (Nazeok in Darjeeling district).

72. *Cloresmus khasianus* Distant, 1901

1901. *Cloresmus khasianus* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77**(37): 15.

Distribution: Assam, Meghalaya, Sikkim and West Bengal.

73. *Cloresmus modestus* Distant, 1901

1901. *Cloresmus modestus* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77**(37): 14, 15.

Distribution: Assam, Meghalaya, Sikkim and West Bengal.

74. *Cloresmus nepalensis* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Nematopus nepalensis* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 4, 14.

Distribution: Assam, Kerala, Sikkim and Tamil Nadu. Elsewhere: Nepal.

Division **COPLPURARIA**

Tribe **Colpurini** Breddin, 1900

Genus *Hygia* Uhler, 1861

1861. Uhler, *Proc Acad. Natur. Sci. Phila* **13**: 287.

Subgenus *Hygia* Uhler, 1861

75. *Hygia (Hygia) erebus* (Distant, 1901)

1901. *Colpura erebus* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77**(37): 18.

Distribution: Assam, Nagaland and West Bengal.

Subgenus *Hygia (Colpura)* Bergroth, 1894

1894. *Colpura* Bergroth, *Revue d'Entomologie* **13**: 154.

76. *Hygia (Colpura) obscura* (Dallas, 1852)

1852. *Lybas obscures* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 463-464.

Distribution: Assam and West Bengal.

77. *Hygia (Colpura) funebris* (Distant, 1901)

1901. *Colpura funebris* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77**(37): 16.

Distribution: Assam and Sikkim.

78. *Hygia (Colpura) lativentris* (Motschulsky, 1866)

1866. *Maccevethus lativentris* Motschulsky, *Bull. Soc. Imp. Natur. Moscou* **39**(1): 188.

Distribution: Assam, Sikkim and West Bengal.

79. *Hygia (Colpura) sulcata* (Paiva, 1919)

1919. *Colpura sulcata* Paiva, *Rec. Ind. Mus. Calcutta* **16**: 357-358, plate 36 fig. 1.

Distribution: Assam, Meghalaya (Garo Hills, above Tura).

Genus *Hygia (Microcolpura)* Breddin, 1900

1900. *Colpura (Microcolpura)* Breddin, *Revue d'Entomologie* **19**: 203.

80. *Hygia (Microcolpura) terebrans* (Breddin, 1906)

1906. *Colpura (Microcolpura) terebrans* Breddin, *Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg.* **50**: 48, 50-51.

Distribution: Assam.

Subgenus *Hygia (Pterocolpura)* Blöte, 1936

1936. *Hygia (Pterocolpura)* Blöte, *Zoölogische Mededeelingen* **19**: 42.

81. *Hygia (Pterocolpura) noctua* (Distant, 1901)

1901. *Colpura noctua* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77**(37): 18-19.

Distribution: Assam.

82. *Hygia (Pterocolpura) nodulosa* (Distant, 1889)

1889. *Lybas nodulosus* Distant, *Ent. Mon. Mag.* **25**: 231.

Distribution: Assam, Meghalaya, Sikkim and West Bengal.

Division **ANISOSCELARIA**

Tribe **Anisoscelini** Laporte, 1832

Genus *Leptoglossus* Guérin-Méneville, 1831

1831. *Leptoglossus* Guérin-Méneville, *Crustaces, Arachnides et Insectes. Zoologie* **2**(2): pl. 12, fig. 9.

83. *Leptoglossus gonagra* (Fabricius, 1775)

1775. *Cimex gonagra* Fabricius, *Systema entomologiae: sistens insectorum classes, ordines, genera, species, adiectis synonymis, locis, descriptionibus, observationibus* 708.

Distribution: Assam and Andaman & Nicobar islands.

Tribe **Dasynini** Bergroth, 1913

Genus *Chinadasynus* Hsiao, 1964

1964. *Chinadasynus* Hsiao, *Acta Scientiarum Naturalium Universitatis Nankaiensis* **5**(1): 19, 21, 28, 35.

84. *Chinadasynus orientalis* (Distant, 1889)

1889. *Pendulinus orientalis* Distant, *Ent. Mon. Mag.* **25**: 231.

Distribution: Assam and Sikkim.

Genus *Dasynus* Burmeister, 1834

1834. *Dasynus* Burmeister, Beiträge zur Zoologie, gesammelt auf einer Reise um die Erde, und W Erichson's und H. Burmeister's Beschreibungen und Abbildungen der von Herrn Meyen auf dieser Reise gesammelten Insekten. Nova Acta Academiae Caesareae Leopoldino-Carolinae Naturae Curiosorum **16**: 297.

85. *Dasynus antennatus* (Kirby, 1891)

1891. *Homoeocerus antennatus* Kirby, *Journal of the Linnean Society, Zoology* **24**: 149–150: 90-91, plate 4, fig. 6.

Distribution: Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

86. *Dasynus fumosus* (Blöte, 1935)

1935. *Amblypelta fumosa* Blöte, *Zoologische Mededeelingen* **18**:214-215.

Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).

87. *Dasynus relatus* Paiva, 1919

1919. *Dasynus relatus* Paiva, *Rec. Ind. Mus. Calcutta* **16**: 358.

Distribution: Assam.

Genus *Odontoparia* Mayr, 1865

1865. *Odontoparia* Mayr, *Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien* **15**: 433.

88. *Odontoparia nicobarensis* Mayr, 1865

1865. *Odontoparia nicobarensis* Mayr, *Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien* **15**: 433.

Distribution: Nicobar Islands.

Genus *Paradasynus* China, 1934

1934. *Paradasynus China*, *Bulletin of Entomological Research* **25**: 189.

89. *Paradasynus rostratus* (Distant, 1908)

1908. *Pendulinus rostratus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota* **4** (2): 473.

Distribution: Maharashtra.

Division **PHYSOMERARIA**

Tribe **Acanthocorini** Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus *Physomerus* Burmeister, 1835

1835. *Physomerus* Burmeister, *Handbuch der Entomologie* 304, 341.

90. *Physomerus grossipes* (Fabricius, 1794)

1794. *Lygaeus grossipes* Fabricius, *Entomologia systematica emendata et aucta secundum classes, ordines, genera, species adjectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus* **4**: 135.

Distribution: Assam, Jharkhand, Kerala, Sikkim and West Bengal.

91. *Physomerus parvulus* Dallas, 1852

1852. *Physomerus parvulus* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 413 – 414.

Distribution: Andaman & Nicobar Islands and Uttarakhand.

Genus *Acanthocoris* Amyot & Serville, 1843
1843. Amyot & Serville, *Histoire naturelle des insectes. Hémiptères* 213 – 214.

92. *Acanthocoris scabrator* (Fabricius, 1803)

1803. *Coreus scabrator* Fabricius, *Systema Rhyngotorum secundum ordines, genera, speciesadjectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus.* 195.

Distribution: Assam, Sikkim and West Bengal (Rohini, Darjeeling and Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri).

Genus *Petalocnemis* Stål, 1854

1854. *Petalocnemis* Stål, *Öfversigt af Kongliga Vetenskaps-Akademiens Förhandlingar* **10**: 259.

93. *Petalocnemis obscura* (Dallas, 1852)

1852. *Acanthocoris obscures* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 518.

Distribution: Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Division **Gonocerariamulsant** & Rey, 1870

Tribe **Gonocerini** Mulsant & Rey, 1870

Genus *Plinachtus* Stål, 1860

1860. *Plinachtus* Stål, *Öfvers. K. Vetensk Akad. Förh. Stockh* **16**: 470.

94. *Plinachtus acicularis* (Fabricius, 1803)

1803. *Alydus acicularis* Fabricius, *Systema Rhyngotorum secundum ordines, genera, speciesadjectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus.* 251.

Distribution: Kerala and Maharashtra.

95. *Plinachtus basalis* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Coreus basalis* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 6, 24.

Distribution: Karnataka.

Genus *Trallianus* Distant, 1902

1902. *Trallianus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota* **1** (Heteroptera): 404.

96. *Trallianus chennelli* Distant, 1902

1902. *Trallianus chennelli* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*.

Rhynchota **1** (Heteroptera): 405.

Distribution: Assam.

Genus *Cletus* Stål, 1860

1860. *Cletus* Stål, Kongliga Svenska Fregattens Eugenies Resa Omkring Jorden, under befäl af C.A. Virgin. Åren 1851-53. III Zoologi, Insekter 236.

97. *Cletus bipunctatus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1840)

1840. *Gonocerus bipunctatus* Herrich-Schäffer, *Die wanzenartigen Insecten* **6**: 9-10.

Distribution : Assam, Karnataka, Manipur, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal (Gopalpur, Birbhum district; Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district; Balarampur, Purulia district). **Elsewhere:** Indonesia and Java.

98. *Cletus bovillus* Distant, 1918

1918. *Cletus bovillus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota. Vol. **7**. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda): 158.

Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura) and West Bengal (Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district).

99. *Cletus calumniator* (Fabricius, 1794)

1794. *Coreus calumniator* Fabricius, *Entomologia systematica emendata et aucta secundum classes, ordines, genera, species adjectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus* **4**: 131.

Distribution: Nagaland and West Bengal (Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district).

100. *Cletus feanus* Distant, 1902

1902. *Cletus feanus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota **1** (Heteroptera): 395.

Distribution: West Bengal (Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district). **Elsewhere:** Burma.

101. *Cletus punctiger* (Dallas, 1852)

1852. *Gonocerus punctiger* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 494.

Distribution: Assam, Manipur and West Bengal.

102. *Cletus punctulatus* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Coreus punctulatus* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 23.

Distribution: Assam, Nagaland and Sikkim.

103. *Cletus rubidiventris* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Coreus rubidiventris* Westwood, A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope. **2**: 6, 23.

Distribution: Karnataka and Maharashtra.

104. *Cletus trigonus* (Thunberg, 1783)

1783. *Cimex trigonus* Thunberg, *Dissertatio entomologica novae insectorum species, sistens, cujus partem secundum* **2**: 37.

Distribution: West Bengal (Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district).

Genus *Cletomorpha* Mayr, 1866

1866. *Cletomorpha* Mayr, *Reise der österreichischen Fregatte Novara um die Erde in den Jahren 1857, 1858, 1859 unter den Befehlen des Commodore B. von Wüllerstorff-Urbair*. Zoologischer Theil, Zweiter Band, 1. Abtheilung, B. Part 2. 120.

105. *Cletomorpha hastata* (Fabricius, 1787)

1787. *Cimex hastatus* Fabricius, *Mantissa insectorum sistens species nuper detectas adjectis synonymis, observationibus, descriptionibus, emendationibus* **2**: 287.

Distribution: Maharashtra and West Bengal (Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district).

106. *Cletomorpha raja* Distant, 1901

1901. *Cletomorpha raja* Distant, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* **77**(41): 423 – 424.

Distribution: Assam (Mungphu), Sikkim and West Bengal (Peshok, Darjeeling district).

107. *Cletomorpha walkeri* Kirby, 1891

1891. *Cletomorpha walkeri* Kirby, *Journal of the Linnean Society, Zoology* **24** (149 – 150): 96-97.

Distribution: West Bengal (Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district). **Elsewhere:** Sri Lanka.

Tribe **Coreini** Leach, 1815

Genus *Haidara* Distant, 1908

1908. *Haidara* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota **4** (2): 474.

108. *Haidara admota* Distant, 1908

1908. *Haidara admota* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota **4** (2): 475.

Distribution: Maharashtra (Mumbai).

109. *Haidara producta* Distant, 1908

1908. *Haidara product Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma.* Rhynchota **4** (2): 474.

Distribution: Maharashtra.

Tribe **Phyllomorphini** Mulsant & Rey, 1870

Genus **Tongorma** Kirkaldy, 1900

1900. *Tongorma* Kirkaldy, *Entomologist* **33**: 242.

110. *Tongorma campbelli* (Distant, 1918)

1918. *Craspedum campbelli* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma.* Rhynchota. Vol. **7**. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 159.

Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).

111. *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood, 1874)

1874. *Phyllomorpha indica* Westwood, *Thesaurus entomologicus oxoniensis* **190**, Plate 36, fig. 1.

Distribution: India.

Subfamily **HYDARINAE**

Division **Hydaria**

Genus **Hydarella** Bergroth, 1925

1925. *Hydarella* Bergroth, *Konowia, Vienna* **4**: 82-85.

112. *Hydarella orientalis* (Distant, 1902)

1902. *Hydara orientalis* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma.* Rhynchota **1** (Heteroptera) 398-399.

Distribution: Sikkim and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Burma, Teinzo, Bhamo.

Subfamily **PSEUDOPHLOCINAE**

Tribe **Clavigrallini** Stål, 1873

Genus **Clavigralla** Spinola, 1837

1837. *Clavigralla Spinola*, *Essai sur les genres d'insectes appartenants à l'ordre des Hémiptères, Lin. ou Rhyngotes, Fab. et à la section des Hétéropères*, Dufour 200-202.

113. *Clavigralla gibbosa* Spinola, 1837

1837. *Clavigralla gibbosa* Spinola, *Essai sur les genres d'insectes appartenants à l'ordre des Hémiptères, Lin. ou Rhyngotes, Fab. et à la section des Hétéropères*, Dufour 202.

Distribution : Karnataka (Chikkaballapura), Maharashtra (Mumbai) and West Bengal (Kolkata and Oodiabani forest, Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district).

114. *Clavigralla scutellaris* (Westwood, 1842)

1842. *Coreus scutellaris* Westwood, *A Catalogue of Hemiptera in the collection of the Rev. F. W. Hope.* **2**: 24.

Distribution: Rajasthan.

Genus **Gralliclava** Dolling, 1978

1978. *Gralliclava* Dolling, *Bull. Br. Mus. (Nat. Hist.) Entomol.* **36**(6): 304.

115. *Gralliclava horrens horrens* (Dohrn, 1860)

1860. *Clavigralla horrens* Dohrn, *Stettin. Entomol. Zeit.* **21**:403.

Distribution: Assam, Maharashtra, Manipur and West Bengal (Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district). **Elsewhere:** Sri Lanka.

Tribe **Pseudophloeini** Stål, 1868

Genus **Hoplolomia** Stål, 1873

1873. *Hoplolomia* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2):82.

116. *Hoplolomia scabricula* Stål, 1873

1873. *Hoplolomia scabricula* Stål, *K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand.* **11**(2):84.

Distribution: Madhya Pradesh.

Genus **Psilolomia** Breddin, 1909

1909. *Psilolomia Breddin*, *Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg.* **53**: 292.

117. *Psilolomia brevitibialis* Breddin, 1909

1909. *Psilolomia brevitibialis* Breddin, *Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg.* **53**: 292.

Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Family **STENOCEPHALIDAE** Dallas, 1852

Division **Stenocephalaria**

Genus **Dicranocephalus** Hahn, 1826

1826. *Dicranocephalus* Hahn, *Icones ad monographium Cimicum* pl. 24.

118. *Dicranocephalus lateralis* (Signoret, 1879)

1879. *Stenocephalus lateralis* Signoret, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France* **1879**:72.

Distribution: Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Malaysia.

Family **ALYDIDAE**

Subfamily **ALYDINAE**

Genus **Daclera** Signoret, 1863

1863. *Daclera* Signoret, *Notes sur l'île de la Réunion (Bourbon)* (2nd edn) **2**:27.

119. *Daclera levana* Distant, 1918

1918. *Daclera levana* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma.* Rhynchota. Vol. **7**. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 162-163, fig. 77.

Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).

Division **Alydaria**

Genus **Euthetus** Dallas, 1852

1852. *Euthetus* Dallas, *List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum* **II**: 467, 479-480.

- 120. *Euthetus atomarius*** Distant, 1918
1918. *Euthetus atomarius* Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota. Vol. 7. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 165.
Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).
- 121. *Euthetus fulvescens*** Distant, 1918
1918. *Euthetus fulvescens* Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota. Vol. 7. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 164-165.
Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).
- 122. *Euthetus khandalana*** Distant, 1918
1918. *Euthetus khandalana* Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota. Vol. 7. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 163-164.
Distribution: Maharashtra (Khandala).
- 123. *Euthetus nigrellus*** Distant, 1918
1918. *Euthetus nigrellus* Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota. Vol. 7. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 164.
Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura and Mysore districts).
- 124. *Euthetus pulchellus*** Dallas, 1852
1852. *Euthetus pulchellus* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum II: 479-480, plate 14, figs 3, 3a, b.
Distribution: North India.
- 125. *Euthetus pulcherrimus*** Bergroth, 1909
1909. *Euthetus pulcherrimus* Bergroth, *Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg.* **53**: 186-188.
Distribution: Maharashtra (Borghat, Mumbai) and Punjab.
Genus *Hypselopus* Burmeister, 1835
1835. *Hypselopus* Burmeister, *Handbuch der Entomologie* **304**, 328-329.
- 126. *Hypselopus mimicus*** Distant, 1918
1918. *Hypselopus mimicus* Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota. Vol. 7. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 168.
Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).
- 127. *Hypselopus pronotalis*** Distant, 1918
1918. *Hypselopus pronotalis* Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota. Vol. 7. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 167, 168, fig. 78.
Distribution: Uttarakhand (Kumaon, Darmoti).
Genus *Nariscus* Stål, 1866
1866. *Nariscus* Stål, *Hemiptera Africana* **2**:8, 100-101.
- 128. *Nariscus fisheri*** (Distant, 1908)
1908. *Akbaratus fisheri* Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota 4 (2) 486-487.
Distribution: Maharashtra (Mumbai), South India, Uttarakhand (Premnagar, Dehradun district).
Genus *Riptortus* Stål, 1860
1860. *Riptortus* Stål, *Öfvers. K. Vetensk Akad. Förh. Stockh* **16**:459, 460.
- 129. *Riptortus linearis*** (Fabricius, 1775)
1775. *Cimex linearis* Fabricius, *Systema entomologiae: sistens insectorum classes, ordines, genera, species, adiectis synonymis, locis, descriptionibus, observationibus* 710.
Distribution: Assam, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal (Kolkata; Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district; Darjeeling district; Shibpur in Howrah district).
- 130. *Riptortus pedestris*** (Fabricius, 1775)
1775. *Cimex pedestris* Fabricius, *Systema entomologiae: sistens insectorum classes, ordines, genera, species, adiectis synonymis, locis, descriptionibus, observationibus* 727.
Distribution : Karnataka, Maharashtra, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Kolkata, Sonarpur in South 24 Parganas district, Cooch Behar district, Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district ; Darjeeling district ; Murshidabad and Puruliya districts).
- 131. *Riptortus strenuus*** Horváth, 1889
1889. *Riptortus strenuus* Horváth, *Természetráji Füzetek* **12**:35-36.
Distribution: Himalayas.
Genus *Tenosius* Stål, 1860
1860. *Tenosius* Stål, *Öfvers.K.VetenskAkad.Förh.Stockh* **16**:459, 460.
- 132. *Tenosius proletarius*** (Schaum, 1853)
1853. *Alydus proletarius* Schaum, *Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin* **1853**:358.
Distribution: West Bengal.
Subfamily MICRELYTERINAE
Tribe Micrelytrini
Genus *Acestra* Dallas, 1852

1852. *Acestra* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum II: 485, 488.

133. *Acestra malayana* Distant, 1903

1903. *Acestra malayana* Distant, *Fasciculi Malayenses*. Zoology Part **2**:245, plate 15 fig. 7.

Distribution: Kerala (parambikulam, Cochin).

Genus *Dulichius* Stål, 1866

1866. *Dulichius* Stål, *Hemiptera Africana* **2**:7, 89-90.

134. *Dulichius inflatus* (Kirby, 1891)

1891. *Formicoris inflatus* Kirby, *Journal of the Linnean Society, Zoology* **24** 149-150:122-123, plate 4 figs 17, 17a.

Distribution: Odisha, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal. **Elsewhere:** Sri Lanka.

Genus *Marcus* Stål, 1865

1865. *Marcus* Stål, *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* **45**:186.

135. *Marcus ornatulus* (Distant, 1908)

1908. *Babaranus ornatulus* Distant, *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Rhynchota **4** (2): 482-483.

Distribution: Assam and West Bengal (Peshok in Darjeeling district). **Elsewhere:** Burma, Tenasserim and Myitta.

Division **Leptocorisaria**

Tribe **Leptocorisini**

Genus *Leptocorisa* Latreille, 1829

1829. *Leptocorisa* Latreille, *Le Règne Animal distribué d'après son organisation, pour servir de base à l'histoire naturelle des animaux et d'Introduction à l'anatomie comparée*. **5**: 196.

136. *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thunberg, 1783)

1783. *Cimex acuta* Thunberg, *Dissertatio entomologica novas insectorum species, sistens, cujus partem secundum* **2**:34.

Distribution: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Odisha, Uttarakhand, and West Bengal (Nort 24 Parganas district, Kolkata district; Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri district and Kalyani, Nadia district).

137. *Leptocorisa lepida* Breddin, 1909

1909. *Leptocorisa lepida* Breddin, *Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg.* **53**:293-294, fig. 23.

Distribution: Maharashtra (Bhandara), Uttar Pradesh (Allahabad and Nandgaon) and Uttarakhand (Dehradun).

138. *Leptocorisa varicornis* (Fabricius, 1783)

Distribution: Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Odisha, Sikkim and West Bengal.

Genus *Stenocoris* Burmeister, 1839

1839. *Stenocoris* Burmeister, *Handbuch der Entomologie* **2**(2):1010.

Subgenus *Stenocoris* (*Stenocoris*) Burmeister, 1839

139. *Stenocoris* (*Stenocoris*) *tipuloides* (De Geer, 1773)

1773. *Cimex tipuloides* De Geer, *Memoires pour servir a l'Histoire des insectes* **3**:354, plate 35, fig. 1.

Distribution: Punjab.

Family **RHOPALIDAE** Amyot & Serville, 1843

Subfamily **SERINETHINAE** Stål, 1873

Genus *Boisea* Kirkaldy, 1910

1910. *Leptocoris* (*Boisea*) Kirkaldy, *Proceedings of the Hawaiian Entomological Society* **2**(3):123.

140. *Boisea coimbatorensis* (Gross, 1960)

1960. *Leptocoris coimbatorensis* Gross, *Records of the South Australian Museum* **13**(4):417.

Distribution: Tamil Nadu (Kadamparai and Chincona in Anaimalai Hills of Coimbatore district).

Genus *Leptocoris* Hahn, 1833

1833. *Leptocoris* Hahn, *Die Wanzenartigen Insecten, getreu nach der Natur abgebildet und beschreiben* **1**:200, pl. XXXII.D-F.

141. *Leptocoris abdominalis abdominalis* (Fabricius, 1803)

1803. *Lygaeus abdominalis* Fabricius, *Systema Rhyngotorum secundum ordines, genera, speciesadjectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus*. 226.

Distribution: Tamil Nadu (Kadamparai and Chincona in Anaimalai Hills of Coimbatore district and Nilagiri Hills in Nilagiri district).

142. *Leptocoris abdominalis taprobanensis* (Dallas, 1852)

1852. *Serinetha taprobanensis* Dallas, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **II**: 461.

Distribution: Tamil Nadu (Kadamparai and Chincona in Anaimalai Hills of Coimbatore district and Nilagiri Hills in Nilagiri district).

143. *Leptocoris augur* (Fabricius, 1781)

1781. *Cimex augurs* Fabricius, Species Insectorum exhibentes eorum differentias specificas, synonyma auctorum, loca natalia, metamorphosin adiectis observationibus, descriptionibus. 2:366.

Distribution: Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Odisha, Puducherry, Tamil Nadu (Coimbatore district), Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

144. *Leptocoris dispar* (Hsiao, 1963)

1963. *Serinetha dispar* Hsiao, Acta Entomologica Sinica **12**:331, 344.

Distribution: Tamil Nadu (Kadamparai and Chincona in Anaimalai Hills of Coimbatore district and Nilagiri Hills in Nilagiri district).

145. *Leptocoris rufomarginatus* (Fabricius, 1794)

1794. *Lygaeus rufomarginatus* Fabricius, Entomologia systematica emendata et aucta secundum classes, ordines, genera, species adiectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus **4**:152.

Distribution: West Bengal.

Subfamily **RHOPALINAE** Amyot & Serville, 1843

Tribe **Rhopalini** Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus *Corizus* Fallén, 1814

1814. *Corizus* Fallén, Specimen novam Hemiptera disponendi methodum exhibens **8**.

146. *Corizus fenestella subsimilis* Horváth, 1917

1917. *Corizus limbatus* Horváth, Ann. Mus. Hungar. **15**:167, 173.

Distribution: South India and Uttarakhand.

147. *Corizus hyoscyami hyoscyami* (Linnaeus, 1758)

1758. *Cimex hyoscyami* Linnaeus, Systema naturae per regna tria naturae, secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis. Editio decima, reformata 447.

Distribution: Himalayas.

Genus *Liorhyssus* Stål, 1870

1870. *Corizus (Liorhyssus)* Stål, K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand. **9**(1): 222.

148. *Liorhyssus hyalinus* (Fabricius, 1794)

1794. *Lygaeus hyalinus* Fabricius, Entomologia systematica emendata et aucta secundum classes, ordines, genera, species adiectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus **4**:168.

Distribution: Punjab.

149. *Liorhyssus rubicundus* (Signoret, 1859)

1859. *Corizus rubicundus* Signoret, Annales de la Société Entomologique de France **37**:86.

Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura), Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri Hills) and Uttarakhand.

Tribe **Niesthreini** Chopra, 1967

Genus *Peliochrous* Stål, 1873

1873. *Peliochrous* Stål, K. Svens. Vet.-Akad. Hand. **11**(2):97, 98.

150. *Peliochrous parvipictus* (Distant, 1918)

1918. *Corizus parvipictus* Distant, The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Rhynchota. Vol. 7. (Homoptera: appendix; Heteroptera: addenda) 168.

Distribution: Karnataka (Chikkaballapura).

Tribe **Chorosomatini** Fieber, 1860

Genus *Agraphopus* Stål, 1872

1872. *Agraphopus* Stål,

Öfvers.K.VetenskAkad.Förh.Stockh **29**(6):55.

151. *Agraphopus lethierryi* Stål, 1872

1872. *Agraphopus lethierryi* Stål,

Öfvers.K.VetenskAkad.Förh.Stockh **29**(6):56.

Distribution: Bihar (Katihar and Purnea

districts), Punjab, South India and West Bengal.

DISCUSSION

The diversity of species is more in the Western Ghats region and in the Deccan plateau region when compared to the other regions of the country. About 44% of Coreoids are recorded from both the regions only. A very less number of species diversity is being seen in the Islands due to their isolation from the mainland. The habitat and climatic conditions plays an important role in determining the species diversity as well as the population density of insects. The Deccan Plateau and the Western ghats are covered by ancient forests which are older than Himalayas, the Plateau is home for rich wildlife. Several sacred evergreen groves contribute to the biodiversity of this ecoregions. These forests nourish the needs of the insects for the successful existence in their habitat. Fossils found here reveal that this region used to be a most evergreen rain forest, far different from today's dry climate forests. The gangetic plain and the Northeast region show the second most diversity of species. 41% of the coreoids were

recorded from this region. Next to this, there are about 37% of the total species of the country were recorded in Himalayan region. The Trans-Himalayan, Semi-arid, Desert, Coasts and islands with a very poor diversity of species.

The species *Molipteryx hardwicki* White, *Helcomeria spinosa* (signoret), *Ochrochira aberrens* (Distant), *Neomictis filicornis* (walker), *Homoeocerus fasciolatus* (Stål), *Homoeocerus punctum* (Dallas) and *Riptortus sternus* Horvath have confined to the Himalayan area only. They were not recorded from any other place. This shows that these species have habituated or adapted to live in the hilly region only. *Prionolomia cardoni* Lethierry, *Cletus trigonus* (Thunberg), *Tenosius proletarius* Sehaum, *Hypselopus pronotalis* Distant, *Corizus hyoscyami hyoscyami* (Linnaeus), *Liorhyssus hyalinus* (Fabricius), *Liorhyssus rubicundus* (Signoret) and *Leptocoris rufomarginatus* (Fabricius) were recorded from the Gangetic plain only. *Mictis gallina* Dallas, *Aspilosterna pictor* (Fabricius), *Anoplocnemis binotata* Distant, *Homoeocerus (Tlaponius) atkinsoni* Distant, *Homoeocerus (Tlaponius) badgleyi* Distant, *Homoeocerus (Tlaponius) indus* Distant, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) subjectus* Walker, *Notobitus abdominalis* Distant, *Cloesmus antennatus* Distant, *Hygia (Pterocolpura) noctua* (Distant), *Hygia (Colpura) sulcata* (Paiva), *Hygia (Microcolpura) terebrans* (Breddin), *Dasynus relatus* Paiva, *Trallianus chennelli* Distant and *Cletus calumniator* (Fabricius) were recorded from the Northeastern region alone. *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) lacertosus* Distant, *Hoplolomia scabricula* Stål and *Liorhyssus hyalinus* (Fabricius) are seen only in the semi-arid region. *Clavigralla scutellaris* (Westwood) is the only one species recorded from the desert area but not from any other area. The species *Odontoparia nicobarensis* Mayr recorded from Nicobar islands alone.

Ochrochira albiditarsis (Westwood), *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood), *Riptortus strenuus* Horváth and *Corizus hyoscyami hyoscyami*

(Linnaeus) were available in Trans-Himalaya and in many other biogeographic regions also. The species *Ochrochira albiditarsis* (Westwood), *Ochrochira biplagiata* (Walker), (*Mictis tenebrosa* Fabricius), *Anoplocnemis phasianus* (Fabricius), *Anoplocnemis protracta* (Herrich-Schäffer), *Petillopsis calcar* (Dallas), *Petillopsis patulicollis* (Walker), *Dalader acuticosta* Amyot & Serville, *Dalader planiventris* (Westwood), *Dalader planiventris* (Westwood), *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) albiguttulus* Stål, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) albiguttulus* Stål, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) angulatus* Westwood, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) concisus* Walker, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) simiolus* Distant, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) stricicornis* Scott, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) walkeri* Kirby, *Homoeocerus (Tlaponius) montanus* Distant, *Homoeocerus (Tlaponius) puncticornis* (Burmeister), *Homoeocerus (Tlaponius) serrifer* (Westwood), *Prismatocerus signatus* (Walker), *Anhomoeus nepalensis* (Distant), *Prismatocerus inornatus* (Stål), *Notobitus excellens* Distant, *Notobitus serripes* (Dallas), *Cloesmus khasianus* Distant, *Cloesmus nepalensis* (Westwood), *Hygia (Pterocolpura) nodulosa* (Distant), *Hygia (Colpura) funebris* (Distant), *Hygia (Colpura) lativentris* (Motschulsky), *Acanthocoris scabrator* (Fabricius), *Cletus calumniator* (Fabricius), *Cletomorpha raja* Distant, *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood), *Hydarella orientalis* (Distant), *Acestra malayana* Distant, *Marcus ornatulus* (Distant) and *Riptortus linearis* (Fabricius) are occurring both in the Himalayan region and in other regions also.

Ochrochira albiditarsis (Westwood), *Homoeocerus (Tlaponius) puncticornis* (Burmeister), *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood) and *Stenocoris (Stenocoris) tipuloides* (De Geer) are recorded from the desert as well as other biogeographic zones. *Ochrochira albiditarsis* (Westwood), *Anoplocnemis phasianus* (Fabricius), *Homoeocerus (Tlaponius) puncticornis* (Burmeister), *Aschistocoris*

Table-1. The biogeographical species distribution of the superfamily: Coreoidea

No	Name of the species	Trans Himalayas	Himalayas	Desert	Semi arid	Western Ghats	Deccan Plateau	Gangetic Plain	Northeast India	Coasts	Islands
1.	<i>Molipteryx hardwickii hardwickii</i> (White, 1839)		+								
2.	<i>Derepteryx grayii</i> White, 1839		+					+			
3.	<i>Helcomeria spinosa</i> (Signoret, 1851)		+								
4.	<i>Prionolomia cardoni</i> Lethierry, 1891							+			
5.	<i>Prionolomia fulvicornis</i> (Fabricius, 1787)		+					+			
6.	<i>Prionolomia gigas</i> Distant, 1879		+								
7.	<i>Prionolomiopsis amplicollis</i> (Stål, 1873)								+		
8.	<i>Ochrochira aberrans</i> (Distant, 1889)		+								
9.	<i>Ochrochira albiditarsis</i> (Westwood, 1842)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
10.	<i>Ochrochira biplagiata</i> (Walker, 1871)		+						+		
11.	<i>Ochrochira pallescens</i> Distant, 1889								+		
12.	<i>Ochrochira palliditarsis</i> Stål, 1873								+		
13.	<i>Mictis gallina</i> Dallas, 1852								+		
14.	<i>Mictis macra</i> Stål, 1865				+	+					
15.	<i>Mictis tenebrosa</i> (Fabricius, 1787)		+					+	+		
16.	<i>Aspilosterna pictor</i> (Fabricius, 1794)								+		
17.	<i>Neomictis filicornis</i> (Walker, 1871)		+								
18.	<i>Anoplocnemis binotata</i> Distant, 1918								+		
19.	<i>Anoplocnemis phasianus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)		+		+	+	+	+	+		
20.	<i>Anoplocnemis protracta</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850)		+					+			
21.	<i>Xyrophoreus cristatus</i> Brailovsky & Barrera, 2000					+	+				
22.	<i>Trematocoris lobipes</i> (Westwood, 1842)						+	+			
23.	<i>Trematocoris notatipes</i> Walker, 1871							+			
24.	<i>Petillopsis calcar</i> (Dallas, 1852)		+				+	+	+		
25.	<i>Petillopsis patulicollis</i> (Walker, 1871)		+						+		
26.	<i>Dalader acuticosta</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843		+					+	+		
27.	<i>Dalader planiventris</i> (Westwood, 1842)		+			+	+	+	+		

...Table-1. The biogeographical species distribution of the superfamily: Coreoidea

28.	<i>Brachytes bicolor</i> Westwood, 1842					+	+		+		
29.	<i>Aschistocoris brevicornis</i> (Dallas, 1852)		+		+						
30.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) albiguttulus</i> Stål, 1873		+						+		
31.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) albiventris</i> Dallas, 1852					+	+				
32.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) angulatus</i> Westwood, 1842		+			+	+				
33.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) biguttatus</i> Westwood, 1842		+								
34.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) concisus</i> Walker, 1871		+							+	
35.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) fasciolatus</i> Stål, 1873		+								
36.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) graminis</i> (Fabricius, 1803)		+								
37.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) javanicus</i> Dallas, 1852									+	
38.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) lacertosus</i> Distant, 1889					+					
39.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) macula</i> Dallas, 1852						+	+			
40.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) simiolus</i> Distant, 1902		+							+	
41.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) stricornis</i> Scott, 1874		+				+	+	+	+	
42.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) subjectus</i> Walker, 1871									+	
43.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) tinctus</i> Distant, 1883									+	
44.	<i>Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) walkeri</i> Kirby, 1892		+						+	+	
45.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) atkinsoni</i> Distant, 1901									+	
46.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) badgleyi</i> Distant, 1908									+	
47.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) indus</i> Distant, 1918						+	+	+		
48.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) laevilineus</i> Stål, 1873						+	+		+	
49.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) montanus</i> Distant, 1901						+	+			
50.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) nigradorsum</i> Horváth, 1889		+				+	+			
51.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) picturatus</i> Distant, 1918						+	+			
52.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) puncticornis</i> (Burmeister, 1834)										+
53.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) punctum</i> Dallas, 1852		+								
54.	<i>Homoeocerus (Tliponius) serrifer</i> (Westwood, 1842)		+							+	
55.	<i>Prismatocerus apicicornis</i>						+	+			

....Table-1. The biogeographical species distribution of the superfamily: Coreoidea

	(Distant, 1918)											
56.	<i>Prismatocerus borealis</i> (Distant, 1918)					+	+					
57.	<i>Prismatocerus cordiger</i> (Stål, 1860)					+	+					
58.	<i>Prismatocerus inornatus</i> (Stål, 1873)					+	+	+				
59.	<i>Prismatocerus prominulus</i> (Dallas, 1852)					+	+					
60.	<i>Prismatocerus sigillatus</i> (Stål, 1873)		+						+			
61.	<i>Prismatocerus signatus</i> (Walker, 1871)		+			+	+	+				
62.	<i>Anhomoeus nepalensis</i> (Distant, 1908)		+						+			
63.	<i>Anhomoeus sulcatus</i> (Distant, 1908)		+						+			
64.	<i>Omanocoris versicolor</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1841)		+		+	+	+					
65.	<i>Notobitus abdominalis</i> Distant, 1901									+		
66.	<i>Notobitus dorsalis</i> (Westwood, 1842)						+	+	+			
67.	<i>Notobitus excellens</i> Distant, 1879		+							+		
68.	<i>Notobitus marginalis</i> (Westwood, 1842)								+	+		
69.	<i>Notobitus meleagris</i> (Fabricius, 1787)						+	+	+			
70.	<i>Notobitus serripes</i> (Dallas, 1850)		+							+		
71.	<i>Cloresmus antennatus</i> Distant, 1908								+	+		
72.	<i>Cloresmus khasianus</i> Distant, 1901		+						+	+		
73.	<i>Cloresmus modestus</i> Distant, 1901		+						+	+		
74.	<i>Cloresmus nepalensis</i> (Westwood, 1842)		+				+	+		+		
75.	<i>Hygia (Hygia) erebus</i> (Distant, 1901)		+						+	+		
76.	<i>Hygia (Colpura) obscura</i> (Dallas, 1852)								+	+		
77.	<i>Hygia (Colpura) funebris</i> (Distant, 1901)		+							+		
78.	<i>Hygia (Colpura) lativentris</i> (Motschulsky, 1866)		+						+	+		
79.	<i>Hygia (Colpura) sulcata</i> (Paiva, 1919)									+		
80.	<i>Hygia (Microcolpura) terebrans</i> (Breddin, 1906)									+		
81.	<i>Hygia (Pterocolpura) noctua</i> (Distant, 1901)									+		
82.	<i>Hygia (Pterocolpura) nodulosa</i> (Distant, 1889)		+						+	+		

....Table-1. The biogeographical species distribution of the superfamily: Coreoidea

83.	<i>Leptoglossus gonagra</i> (Fabricius, 1775)								+		+
84.	<i>Chinadasynus orientalis</i> (Distant, 1889)		+						+		
85.	<i>Dasynus antennatus</i> (Kirby, 1891)					+	+				
86.	<i>Dasynus fumosus</i> (Blöte, 1935)						+				
87.	<i>Dasynus relatus</i> Paiva, 1919								+		
88.	<i>Odontoparia nicobarensis</i> Mayr, 1865										+
89.	<i>Paradasynus rostratus</i> (Distant, 1908)					+	+				
90.	<i>Physomerus grossipes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		+			+	+	+	+		
91.	<i>Physomerus parvulus</i> Dallas, 1852								+		
92.	<i>Acanthocoris scabrator</i> (Fabricius, 1803)		+							+	
93.	<i>Petalocnemis obscura</i> (Dallas, 1852)					+	+			+	
94.	<i>Plinactus acicularis</i> (Fabricius, 1803)					+	+				
95.	<i>Plinactus basalis</i> (Westwood, 1842)								+		
96.	<i>Trallianus chennelli</i> Distant, 1902									+	
97.	<i>Cletus bipunctatus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1840)		+			+	+	+	+		
98.	<i>Cletus bovillus</i> Distant, 1918					+	+				
99.	<i>Cletus calumniator</i> (Fabricius, 1794)									+	
100.	<i>Cletus feanus</i> Distant, 1902								+		
101.	<i>Cletus punctiger</i> (Dallas, 1852)								+	+	
102.	<i>Cletus punctulatus</i> (Westwood, 1842)		+								+
103.	<i>Cletus rubidiventris</i> (Westwood, 1842)					+	+				
104.	<i>Cletus trigonus</i> (Thunberg, 1783)								+		
105.	<i>Cletomorpha hastata</i> (Fabricius, 1787)					+	+	+			
106.	<i>Cletomorpha raja</i> Distant, 1901		+						+	+	
107.	<i>Cletomorpha walkeri</i> Kirby, 1891								+		
108.	<i>Haidara admota</i> Distant, 1908					+	+				
109.	<i>Haidara producta</i> Distant, 1908					+	+				
110.	<i>Tongorma campbelli</i> (Distant, 1918)					+	+				
111.	<i>Tongorma indicum</i> (Westwood, 1874)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

....Table-1. The biogeographical species distribution of the superfamily: Coreoidea

11 2.	<i>Hydarella orientalis</i> (Distant, 1902)		+				+	+			
11 3.	<i>Clavigralla gibbosa</i> Spinola, 1837					+	+				
11 4.	<i>Clavigralla scutellaris</i> (Westwood, 1842)			+							
11 5.	<i>Gralliclava horrens horrens</i> (Dohrn, 1860)						+	+	+		
11 6.	<i>Hoplolomia scabricula</i> Stål, 1873				+						
11 7.	<i>Psilolomia brevitibialis</i> Breddin, 1909					+	+				
11 8.	<i>Dicranocephalus lateralis</i> (Signoret, 1879)					+	+				
11 9.	<i>Daclera levana</i> Distant, 1918					+	+				
12 0.	<i>Euthetus atomarius</i> Distant, 1918					+	+				
12 1.	<i>Euthetus fulvescens</i> Distant, 1918					+	+				
12 2.	<i>Euthetus khandalana</i> Distant, 1918			+	+	+					
12 3.	<i>Euthetus nigrellus</i> Distant, 1918					+	+				
12 4.	<i>Euthetus pulchellus</i> Dallas, 1852			+				+			
12 5.	<i>Euthetus pulcherrimus</i> Bergroth, 1909			+	+	+					
12 6.	<i>Hypselopus mimicus</i> Distant, 1918					+	+				
12 7.	<i>Hypselopus pronotalis</i> Distant, 1918						+				
12 8.	<i>Nariscus fisheri</i> (Distant, 1908)					+	+	+			
12 9.	<i>Riptortus linearis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)		+		+	+	+	+	+		
13 0.	<i>Riptortus pedestris</i> (Fabricius, 1775)		+			+	+	+			
13 1.	<i>Riptortus strenuus</i> Horvath, 1889	+			+			+			
13 2.	<i>Tenosius proletarius</i> (Schaum, 1853)							+			
13 3.	<i>Acestra malayana</i> Distant, 1903		+			+	+	+			
13 4.	<i>Dulichius inflatus</i> (Kirby, 1891)						+	+			
13 5.	<i>Marcus ornatulus</i> (Distant, 1908)		+					+	+		
13 6.	<i>Leptocoris acuta</i> (Thunberg, 1783)					+	+	+			
13 7.	<i>Leptocoris lepida</i> Breddin, 1909				+	+	+	+			
13 8.	<i>Leptocoris varicornis</i> (Fabricius, 1783)		+		+	+	+	+	+		
13	<i>Stenocoris (Stenocoris)</i>			+	+						

....Table-1. The biogeographical species distribution of the superfamily: Coreoidea

9.	<i>tipuloides</i> (De Geer, 1773)										
14 0.	<i>Boisea coimbatorensis</i> (Gross, 1960)					+	+				
14 1.	<i>Leptocoris abdominalis abdominalis</i> (Fabricius, 1803)					+	+	+	+		
14 2.	<i>Leptocoris abdominalis taprobanensis</i> (Dallas, 1852)					+	+				
14 3.	<i>Leptocoris augur</i> (Fabricius, 1781)					+	+	+			
14 4.	<i>Leptocoris dispar</i> (Hsiao, 1963)					+	+				
14 5.	<i>Leptocoris rufomarginatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)								+		
14 6.	<i>Corizus fenestella subsimilis</i> Horváth, 1917					+	+	+			
14 7.	<i>Corizus hyoscyami hyoscyami</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+							+		
14 8.	<i>Liorhyssus hyalinus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)					+					
14 9.	<i>Liorhyssus rubicundus</i> (Signoret, 1859)								+		
15 0.	<i>Peliochrous parvipictus</i> (Distant, 1918)								+		
15 1.	<i>Agraphopus lethierryi</i> Stål, 1872					+	+				

brevicornis (Dallas), *Omanocoris versicolor* (Herrich-Schäffer), *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood), *Stenocoris (Stenocoris) tipuloides* (De Geer), *Leptocorisa lepida* Breddin, *Leptocorisa varicornis* (Fabricius), *Euthetus khandalana* Distant, *Euthetus pulchellus* Dallas, *Euthetus pulcherrimus* Bergroth and *Riptortus linearis* (Fabricius) are concurrently occurring in the Semi-arid and various other biogeographic regions.

The following species are simultaneously occurring in the Himalayan and Gangetic Plain regions. They are : *Derepteryx grayii* White, *Ochrochira biplagiata* (Walker), *Anoplocnemis phasianus* (Fabricius), *Anoplocnemis protracta* (Herrich-Schäffer), *Petillopsis calcar* (Dallas), *Dalader acuticosta* Amyot & Serville, *Dalader planiventris* (Westwood), *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) albiguttulus* Stål, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) angulatus* Westwood, *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) puncticornis* (Burmeister), *Prismatocerus sigillatus* (Stål), *Prismatocerus signatus*

(Walker), *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) striicornis* Scott, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) walkeri* Kirby, *Anhomoeus sulcatus* (Distant), *Prismatocerus inornatus* (Stål), *Cloesmus khasianus* Distant, *Cloesmus modestus* Distant, *Hygia (Hygia) erebus* (Distant), *Hygia (Pterocolpura) nodulosa* (Distant), *Hygia (Colpura) lativentris* (Motschulsky), *Physomerus grossipes* (Fabricius), *Cletus bipunctatus* (Herrich-Schäffer), *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood), *Hydarella orientalis* (Distant), *Leptocorisa varicornis* (Fabricius), *Marcus ornatulus* (Distant) and *Riptortus linearis* (Fabricius).

The species namely *Ochrochira albiditarsis* (Westwood), *Mictis macra* Stål, *Anoplocnemis phasianus* (Fabricius), *Dalader planiventris* (Westwood), *Brachytes bicolor* Westwood, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) albiventris* Dallas, *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) angulatus* Westwood, *Prismatocerus apicornis* (Distant), *Prismatocerus cordiger* (Stål), *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) laevilineus* Stål,

Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) macula Dallas, *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) montanus* Distant, *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) nigradorsum* Horváth, *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) picturatus* Distant, *Prismatocerus borealis* (Distant), *Prismatocerus prominulus* (Dallas), *Prismatocerus inornatus* (Stål), *Prismatocerus signatus* (Walker), *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) puncticornis* (Burmeister), *Homoeocerus (Anacanthocoris) striicornis* Scott, *Omanocoris versicolor* (Herrich-Schäffer), *Notobitus dorsalis* (Westwood), *Notobitus meleagris* (Fabricius), *Cloesmus nepalensis* (Westwood), *Dasynus antennatus* (Kirby), *Paradasynus rostratus* (Distant), *Physomerus grossipes* (Fabricius), *Petalocnemis obscura* (Dallas), *Plinactus acicularis* (Fabricius), *Cletus bipunctatus* (Herrich-Schäffer), *Cletus bovillus* Distant, *Cletus rubidiventris* (Westwood), *Cletomorpha hastata* (Fabricius), *Haidara admota* Distant, *Haidara producta* Distant, *Tongorma campbelli* (Distant), *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood), *Dicranocephalus lateralis* (Signoret), *Stenocoris (Stenocoris) tipuloides* (De Geer), *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thunberg), *Leptocorisa lepida* Breddin, *Leptocorisa varicornis* (Fabricius), *Acestra malayana* Distant, *Daclera levana* Distant, *Euthetus atomarius* Distant, *Euthetus fulvescens* Distant, *Euthetus khandalana* Distant, *Euthetus nigrellus* Distant, *Euthetus pulcherrimus* Bergroth, *Nariscus fisheri* (Distant), *Hypselopus mimicus* Distant, *Riptortus linearis* (Fabricius), *Riptortus pedestris* (Fabricius), *Boisea coimbatorensis* (Gross), *Corizus fenestella subsimilis* Horváth, *Peliochrous parvipictus* (Distant), *Leptocorisa augur* (Fabricius), *Leptocorisa dispar* (Hsiao), *Leptocorisa rufomarginatus* (Fabricius), *Leptocorisa abdominalis abdominalis* (Fabricius), *Leptocorisa abdominalis taprobanensis* (Dallas) and *Agraphopus lethierryi* Stål are simultaneously occurred in more than two biogeographic regions in particular their occurrence was mainly noticed in both the Western Ghats and the Deccan Plateau. *Ochrochira albiditarsis* (Westwood), *Leptoglossus gonagra* (Fabricius), *Physomerus parvulus* Dallas and *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood) are being recorded from both the Islands and other biogeographic regions also.

Ochrochira albiditarsis (Westwood), *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) puncticornis* (Burmeister) and *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood) are concurrently occurring in the coastal areas and also in the other biogeographic regions.

The species *Ochrochira albiditarsis* (Westwood), *Homoeocerus (Tliponius) puncticornis* (Burmeister, 1834 and Deivendran, 2015) and *Tongorma indicum* (Westwood) are endemic to India.

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